

A philosophical discussion on fundamental entities based on the structural dynamics of space

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Three hypotheses are stated here. First one is about time, where time is expelled from a dynamic local physical system and illustrated as a non-physical but mathematical element in the so-called time domain equations. Second one is for relation between event value and time rate value (value at time domain) of a physical entity and according to this hypothesis relativistic event mass related value of a photon is calculated which is found as $7.3623002 \times 10^{-51}$ Kg.s. The last one is on space where structural dynamics of the space is considered for the notion of mass, energy and other fundamental entities. Based on these hypotheses findings are- (1) Kg unit is a time rate quantity (value at time domain) not an event (intrinsic) quantity (2) There is no singularity in the black hole. (3) Explanation of wave-particle duality and back ground philosophy of Schrödinger wave function (4) The universe always has net null energy and so net null mass. (5) There is a quantum explanation of slow event (so-called slow time) in a gravitational field. (6) Space can be destroyed or birth of white hole is possible. (7) Explanation of diffraction and interference of light using momentum of light and space.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a marvelous paper titled “Does the Inertia of a Body Depend upon its Energy Content?” [1][2] Albert Einstein said about his previous paper titled ‘On the electrodynamics of moving bodies’ [3][4]. There Albert Einstein stated that he based himself upon the Maxwell-Hertz equations for empty space along with Maxwell’s expression for the electromagnetic energy of space, and also on the following principle: The laws governing the changes of state of physical systems do not depend on which one of two coordinate systems moving in uniform parallel translation relative to each other these changes of state are referred to (principle of relativity) [1] [2].

He also stated that the principle of the constancy of the velocity of light which he used in his previous paper is of course contained in Maxwell’s equations and all those fundamental principles were also used in his current paper [1] [2].

His statement show that Maxwell’s expression is the expression for the electromagnetic energy of space, and the constancy of the velocity of light is contained in Maxwell’s equations.

Moreover, in another paper published in 1905 Albert Einstein stated the electromagnetic radiation as electromagnetic state of space [5][6].

Hence, we can say here that according to A. Einstein electromagnetic radiation (light) is a special property (a particular state) of space and the speed of light is constant due to the character of space.

Albert Einstein also said, “It followed from the special theory of relativity that mass and energy are both but different manifestations of the same thing – a somewhat unfamiliar conception for the average mind. Furthermore,

the equation E is equal to $m c^2$, in which energy is put equal to mass, multiplied by the square of the velocity of light, showed that very small amounts of mass may be converted into a very large amount of energy and vice versa. The mass and energy were in fact equivalent, according to the formula mentioned above. This was demonstrated by Cockcroft and Walton in 1932, experimentally” [7].

Next, we will take an intuitive decision regarding the term “the same thing” of the above statement.

In the theory of general relativity Einstein expressed the gravitation as the curvature of spacetime [8][9].

In a nut shell it can be said that space is a vital element of Albert Einstein’s thoughts.

On the other hand, according to C. Rovelli and L. Smolin space is quantized [10].

According to the theory of special relativity of Einstein time is a local entity [3][4]. If a constant relative speed exists between two systems, then duration of an event is different when it occurred at these two different systems [3][4].

Taking indication form the above-mentioned papers here is a try to describe all the fundamental elements of the universe from the view of dynamic structure of space and by considering “time” only as a mathematical term not as a physical entity.

II. HYPOTHESIS ABOUT TIME

Suppose, some mutually dependent events (interactions) create a dynamic local physical system and these events are independent from other events of the universe. Dependency means an event starts only when previous event/events occurred completely on which it depends. Element of state of this system at particular moment is a physical entity created by an event of this system.

Suppose, when the state of this dynamic local physical system reached at S_0 all events of this system stop.

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Now, if time is an event independent element then it will draw its stamp on every physical entity of the state S_0 . In that case system state will change from S_0 to another state suppose to S_1 . As all events of this system are stopped, according to the hypothesis stated above there will be no change of any physical entity of this system. Hence, state will remain at S_0 . It means that time passing/flowing are also stopped with event stopping.

So, according to above discussion, time cannot be an event independent element.

We know that time is not a universal element rather it is a local element [3][4]. So, let's try to find out the local time element for this system.

If we run intuitive investigation over all physical entities of this system, we will not find any physical entity which is supreme to others. It means that there is no physical entity in this system which can be treated as local time element for this system. So, local time element for this system must be a non-physical element.

At this stage we can say that according to the above discussion, time is an event dependent and non-physical element. It indicates no existence of time in a dynamic local physical system.

In a dynamic local physical system, there is only the events which depend only on the structural dynamics of local space.

But, in order to do comparative discussion between two independent dynamic local physical systems we need a third independent dynamic local physical system. At first, we find out the event chain in the third independent dynamic local physical system. Then an event of first/second system is positioned in the event chain of third system or express equivalent amount of the event chain of third system according to per event of first/second system. This equivalent amount of the event chain of third system according to per event of first/second system is called the duration of an event of first/second system. These actions are the basis of time domain equations of first/second system in respect of third system.

It should be noted here that 'time' of time domain equations is not the Newtonian time or not a physical element rather just a mathematical element. This mathematical element is used to indicate the position of an event of first/second system in the event chain of third system or to express equivalent amount of the event chain of third system according to per event of first/second system.

Equivalent amount of the event chain of third system per event of first/second system cannot be zero rather it must have a minimum value. It means duration of an event of first/second system must be equivalent to at least a minimum amount of the event chain of third system. So, duration of an event of first/second system cannot be zero. Again, duration of an event of first/second system cannot be equivalent to an arbitrary amount of the event chain of third system. It means duration of an event of first/second system is quantized.

This event chain of third system is nothing but the series of tick of our wrist watch, series of swing of a pendulum of our drawing room, series of events at atomic clock etc.

We should keep in mind that time domain equations of the independent dynamic local physical systems are just a mathematical technique which brings the systems in a common platform in order to do comparative discussion among themselves.

In this paper the term 'time' is used according to the above-mentioned concept.

III. HYPOTHETICAL RELATION BETWEEN EVENT VALUE AND TIME RATE VALUE OF A PHYSICAL ENTITY

Physical entities in the universe are the results of events (interactions) occurred at quantum scale. Suppose, in a dynamic local physical system an event (K) creates a physical entity (X) and duration of this event is T (an equivalent amount of an independent chain of events), event value (value at dynamic local physical system) and time rate value (value at time domain) of this physical entity is X_e and X_u . This time rate value is an element of time domain equation of that event.

Hence, by definition-

$$X_u = \frac{X_e}{T} \quad (1)$$

We know that $f = 1/T$, where f is frequency of an event (f is also an element of time domain equation of that event) and T is time needed for complete occurrence of that event. So, now we can write-

$$X_u = X_e f \quad (2)$$

We know that in International System of Units (SI) second (s) is unit for time in time domain equation. Suppose x is the unit for time rate value of physical entity X . So, unit for event value of that physical entity is $x.s$.

In other way, if $x.s$ is unit for event value of a physical entity then, x must be the unit for time rate value of that physical entity.

Event value of a physical entity is nothing but the so-called intrinsic value of that physical entity in that dynamic local physical system.

IV. RELATIVISTIC EVENT MASS OF A PHOTON

Due to quantum nature of light its energy equation is as bellow [5][6][12].

$$E = hf \quad (3)$$

where E is energy per second of photon stream (not energy of a single photon), h is Planck constant, f is frequency of photon in the stream. That means h amount of energy is associated with each photon (impact energy of a single photon) and number of photons is f which impact in one second.

It should be noted here that equation no. (3) is a time domain equation.

Though photon has zero rest mass, according to Compton theory [13] it has momentum (here, momentum in time domain) when it travels at the speed of light. So, this momentum and corresponding mass (here, mass in time domain) are relativistic. Finite value of photon speed indicates that it has relativistic intrinsic (so-called) mass. The relativistic momentum is hf/c , where c is the speed of light [13].

According to the postulates of special theory of relativity of Einstein any parameter of photon we measure is relativistic and the relative speed between observer and photon is speed of light c .

So, not only mass and momentum, energy of a photon traveling at speed of light is also relativistic. Hence, according to Einstein's special theory of relativity $E = mc^2$, where, E is relativistic energy of a photon, m is relativistic mass of a photon, c is the speed of light[1][2][3][4].

It should be also noted here that $E = mc^2$ is a time domain equation.

From previous discussion we see that according to Newton's second law, force (N) is a time rate value (an element of time domain equation) in relativistic situation. Hence the energy (J) is also a time rate value (an element of time domain equation) in relativistic situation because, $1J = 1N.m$

Now, according to the hypothesis stated above, unit $J.s$ is the unit of an event value of energy.

We know that in International System of Units (SI), unit for h is $Kg.m^2.s^{-1}$ or $J.s$. Hence, according to the hypothesis stated above h is the event value of energy of a photon (energy quanta). So, if we calculate photon mass using h , this photon mass value must be the event value.

As energy associated with each photon is h ,

$$mc^2 = h \quad (4)$$

In International System of Units (SI), unit for h is $Kg.m^2.s^{-1}$, unit for c is $m.s^{-1}$, hence, unit for relativistic mass (m) of a photon is $Kg.s$. This unit for relativistic mass of a photon is similar to the unit of an event value of a physical entity with an indication that during calculation of h measuring of mass (in Kg unit) is a time rate value (an element of time domain equation). So, it can be said that h/c^2 is the relativistic event mass of a photon.

Putting $h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} Kg.m^2.s^{-1}$ and $c = 3 \times 10^8 m.s^{-1}$ we find $h/c^2 = 7.3623002 \times 10^{-51} Kg.s$

We know that space is quantized [10]. Due to quantized nature of space, size of an event is quantized, as

well as, by definition event is also a discrete phenomenon with respect of time (an independent chain of events). It indicates that the relativistic event mass of a photon is a discrete entity. It means that in a region of space relativistic event mass of a photon is discontinuous with respect of time. How is it possible? It is possible only when in a region of space existence of a photon is discontinuous with respect of time. What does it mean? It means that in a region of space photon exists only with photon creation event and when there is no photon creation event there is no photon's existence.

Above discussion indicates that existence of photon is discontinuous both in time (an independent chain of events) and space (According to the hypotheses stated in this paper time is a non-physical element and space is a physical element. Here, they are treated as separate elements).

Zero rest mass and constant speed of photon support the above argument.

V. HYPOTHESIS ON SPACE

A. Space as mother thing

In his statement [7] Albert Einstein indicates another thing ('the same thing') which is a candidate to be considered as mother thing for mass and energy.

Now, let's try to interpret Einstein's mass-energy equivalence equation, $E = mc^2$. In this equation speed of light c is used to make the equivalence. What is c ? c is a distance passed by light in a second. What is distance? Distance is one dimensional structural element of space. So, we see that in mass-energy equivalence equation a structural element of space (distance) is used to make the equivalence. Another observation says that mother thing must exists in common with mass and energy simultaneously.

Now the significant question is, which thing is the perfect candidate for being a mother thing? Isn't it the space? Yes, from above discussion it can be decided here that it is space. Treating the electromagnetic radiation as electromagnetic state of space [5][6] and gravitation as the curvature of spacetime [8][9] are two supporting items for the space to be considered as mother thing of mass and energy.

B. Interpretation of discrete area and volume of space

According to C. Rovelli and L. Smolin area and volume of space is quantized [10]. As area is a two dimensional and volume is a three dimensional structural element of space and both of them take birth from fundamental one dimensional structural element of space, one dimensional structural element of space is also quantized.

C. Structure of space and representation of the state of space

Structure of space is dynamic. Due to the structural dynamics of space it can gain various dynamic states. This philosophy expel steady state of space. From space domain view, among the dynamic states of space which one has minimum density of inherent inertia compared to others can be treated as ground state of space. Consequently from time domain view this ground state of space has minimum momentum compared to others. Momentum (time domain element) is the corresponding element of inertia (space domain element). Inherent inertia of a state indicates sustainability of that state during an event.

All states of space except ground state can be called as deviated states.

Due to an event a piece of space can gain a deviated state from a ground state or vice versa.

Each state of space has its own intrinsic characteristics. Different deviated state of space gives us the sense of different physical entity by relevant event.

Each state of space can be expressed by a vector like $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Here, $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ etc. represent various states of space. \otimes between L_n and θ_n is because uncertainty of individual L_n and its θ_n . In quantum world L_n and θ_n appeared as single item like $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Vector of ground state is $L_0 \otimes \theta_0$ and it may be treated as reference vector. Associated modulus (L_n) of a vector is responsible for a quantum intrinsic sense of mass (sense of event mass) in that region of space and associated angle (θ_n) of a vector is responsible for a quantum intrinsic sense of a physical entity (sense of event value of a physical entity) in that region of space. Note that particular angle (θ_n) is responsible for the quantum sense of a particular type physical entity.

If in a region of space there are more than one deviated state (all having particular associated angle (θ_n)) then a set of vectors can represent the deviated states of that region of space where one vector for one deviated state. If the associated angles are same then the net intrinsic sense of mass in that region of space is equal to number of deviated states times sense of mass given by one associated modulus of a vector and the net intrinsic sense of a physical entity in that region of space is equal to number of deviated states times sense of a physical entity given by one associated angle of a vector.

D. Definition of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$

If we consider the term 'region' as the surface and 'deviated state' as deviation in area ($L = L_n - L_0$) and its direction ($\theta = \theta_n - \theta_0$) then a philosophical relation can be written as bellow-

$$L_n \otimes \theta_n \equiv \hat{A}(S) \quad (5)$$

Here,

S is surface.

\hat{A} is area operator [10] [11].

L is deviation of modulus ($L = L_n - L_0$) of a vector representing the deviated state of space.

θ is deviation of angle ($\theta = \theta_n - \theta_0$) of a vector representing the deviated state of space.

If we rewrite as-

$$\hat{A}(S) = \hat{a}|\hat{A}(S)| \quad (6)$$

Here,

$|\hat{A}(S)|$ is the modulus of area of S .

\hat{a} is direction of the area of S .

Then,

$$L_n \equiv |\hat{A}(S)| \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_n \equiv \hat{a} \quad (8)$$

Above discussion is for the definition of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ in two dimension.

Now, if we shrink the area along any one of the dimensions of the surface upto quantum length (minimum length allowed by quantum mechanics) then the surface become to one dimensional element along the other dimension. This final one dimensional element will give the value and direction of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Direction of a one dimensional element is along its dimension.

E. Event of space as vector operation

A vector representing a deviation in a region of space gives a quantum intrinsic sense of a physical entity by an interaction (event) with other vector/vectors (deviation/deviations in the state of space).

Similarly, a set of vectors representing deviations in a region of space gives the net intrinsic sense of a physical entity by an interaction (event) with other vector/vectors (deviation/deviations in the state of space).

As state of space is dynamic, all interactions (events) are also dynamic.

An interaction (event) may be defined by vector operation of interacting vectors.

For example, cross product (interaction/event) of electric field vector (one deviated state of space) and magnetic field vector (another deviated state of space) gives the sense of photon (physical entity).

As area and volume are two discrete properties of space [10], event cannot be happened at anywhere in the space. Event can be occurred only at event station (a characteristic location of space). Spatial gap between two event stations is the distance (one dimensional element of space). It means event station and distance are discrete element of space.

Distances (s) between any two event stations are may not equal.

F. Momentum of a state of space

At first, we should keep in mind that statements of first and third law of newton are applicable both in space domain and time domain. Statement of second law of newton is applicable only in time domain.

From the second law of Newton we know that time rate of momentum (an element of time domain) change of a body is the measure of applied force (an element of time domain). Also, from the first law of Newton we know that without application of external force state of a system remain unchanged. The character which is behind this is the inertia in space domain and time rate of inertia in time domain. According to the first law value of this character of a system is changed due to an application of external force. So, according to first and second law of newton we can say that in time domain change of momentum means change of value of time rate of inertia.

Space is dynamic means there are occurrence of events one after another.

Suppose, a state of space $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is in a region of space. Quantum movement of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is the cause of dynamic nature of space. One quantum move is one event. This quantum move may be in L_n or θ_n or in both. Quantum move of L_n or θ_n are independent from each other.

We know,

$$p = mv = m \frac{ds}{dt} \quad (9)$$

Where,

p is momentum of a body.

m is mass of that body.

s is displacement of that body.

ds/dt is velocity of that body.

Equation no.(9) is applicable only in non-relativistic classical situation because mass is treated here as in-varient element. But in classical relativistic situation mass is not an in-varient element. Hence, general classical momentum equation should be written as-

$$p = \frac{d(ms)}{dt} = m \frac{ds}{dt} + s \frac{dm}{dt} \quad (10)$$

When mass is in-varient then equation no.(9) and equation no. (10) are same. So, equation no.(10) cover both relativistic and non-relativistic classical situation.

It is seen here that non-relativistic classical momentum is a special case of relativistic classical momentum.

Now let's see into quantum world. In quantum world there is no clear mass boundary of a body. So, displacement of its mass also unclear. Hence mass and its displacement can not be treated as separate entity rather they act as a single entity in the quantum world.

According to our hypothesis mass and its displacement are represented by L_n and θ_n of a state of space. So, fuzzyness in mass and its displacement indicates dynamic nature of the state of space. Contribution of L_n

and θ_n in the dynamic nature of a state of space are responsible for amount of mass and physical entity respectively. If contribution of L_n is z percent in the dynamic nature of a state of space then contribution of θ_n is $100 - z$ percent. It should be noted here that value of z allways has some uncertainty. This is compatible with Heisenberg uncertainty principle.

Though in classical world mass and its displacement can be treated as separate entity and in momentum equation they appeared as product.

So, we can say that $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ indicates the inertia in space domain where $L_n \otimes \theta_n \equiv m \otimes s$. As $L_n \otimes \theta_n \equiv m \otimes s$ is a single entity in quantum world, time rate of it can not be treated as momentum like classical world. But in order to comparative discussion among some $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ they have to bring into a common platform like time domain. First order time derivative of them is an excelent technique to bring them in time domain.

Now, let's try to design wave mechanics for our hypotheses.

State of space is not a static one rather it dynamic. It moves over space and through time (chain of events). Minimum size of the state of space indicates a space quanta.

$L_n \otimes \theta_n$ has an associated wave function $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$. It is equivalent to the above mentioned first order time derivative of a state of space.

$$\frac{\partial(m \otimes s)}{\partial t} \equiv \frac{\partial(L_n \otimes \theta_n)}{\partial t} \equiv \frac{\partial[\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi)]}{\partial t} \equiv \Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t) \quad (11)$$

According to the second law of newton $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ changes after an event. Because in an event force is effective means there is a change of inertia means there is a change of $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$.

Suppose, $L_1 \otimes \theta_1$ and $L_2 \otimes \theta_2$ interact with each other. Then, $\Psi_{L_1 \otimes \theta_1}(x, t)$ and $\Psi_{L_2 \otimes \theta_2}(x, t)$ will change after interaction. If $\Psi_{L_1 \otimes \theta_1}(x, t)$ increases by K amount then, $\Psi_{L_2 \otimes \theta_2}(x, t)$ decreases by K amount and vice versa. It means that when a set of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ interact with each other then, the net arithmetic sum of values of all $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ remain unchanged. It is compatible to the conservation law of momentum (a law in time domain).

If there is same period/integer multiple of a fundamental period for up and down of all $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ then, those $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ create a dynamic equilibrium system otherwise they create a dynamic non-equilibrium system.

As modulus (L_n) and direction (θ_n) only combinedly can express a unique area in space domain, $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ only can indicates a unique entity in time domain by the action of a proper operator.

According to our hypothesis $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ is nothing but the wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ of Schrodinger equation of a quantum system.

Hence, according to our hypothesis,

$$\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t) = \Psi(x, t) \quad (12)$$

G. Energy according to the dynamics of space

According to this hypothesis energy (an element of time domain equation) can be defined as the capability of a state of space to influence the other state (deviated/ground) of the space.

H. Density of state of space and domination

Depending on the present dynamics there is a maximum limit of net density of states in a region of space. Dominant state is dynamically decided by densities of present states of that region of space. Probability of a state having highest density is highest to be a dominant one. In that case probability of dominant state related event increases and probabilities of submissive states related events decrease. Even in a region of space if density of a state become so high compared to others than submissive states may be expelled from that region of space. In a region of space net number of events increase as the diversity of state increase on that region of space and vice versa.

Probability of a state related event is-

$$P_i = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i}{d_{max}}\right) \quad (13)$$

Here,

n is number of various type states per area/volume in a region of space.

P_i is intrinsic probability of i^{th} state related event per area/volume in a region of space.

d_i is intrinsic density of i^{th} state per area/volume in a region of space.

d_{max} is maximum net intrinsic density of states per area/volume in a region of space which can be possible.

Due to quantum nature of space d_i is not arbitrary. Hence, $\sum_{i=1}^n d_i$, d_{max} and finally P_i are not arbitrary.

VI. EXPLANATION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF Kg UNIT AS TIME RATE VALUE

Previously we have discussed that amount of mass is equivalent to the contribution (z percent) of L_n in the dynamic nature of a state of space. It means in space domain z percent of inertia ($L_n \otimes \theta_n$) is equivalent to mass and remaining $100 - z$ percent of inertia is equivalent to a physical entity. Consequently, in time domain z percent of $(\frac{\partial(L_n \otimes \theta_n)}{\partial t})$ is equivalent to mass and remaining $100 - z$ percent of $(\frac{\partial(L_n \otimes \theta_n)}{\partial t})$ is equivalent to a physical entity.

We find momentum by the action of momentum operator on $\Psi(x, t)$.

So, we can say that mass in Kg unit is an element related to time rate of the contribution of L_n in the dynamic nature of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$.

Suppose, a state of space $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is static in a region of space. That means its associated $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ is null means its associated $\Psi(x, t)$ is null. Hence, this $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ can not give any sense of mass, momentum, energy or any other physical entity.

But time domain discussion shows that mass, momentum, energy and other physical entity exist in quantum system. That means $\Psi(x, t)$ is not null, means $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ exists. It means that at quantum system a state of space cannot be static in a region of space rather it's dynamic.

If in a region of space dynamic nature of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ increase means if inertia increase then in time domain momentum will increase. Increase of momentum indicates possible increase of mass in Kg unit. Finally, density of mass (in Kg unit) will increase on that region of space. A possible way to increase dynamic nature of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is speed up the events on that region of space. An event means a quantum move of a state of space. So, by speeding up a state of space mass density ($Kg/area$ or $Kg/volume$) can be increased in a region of space. This is compatible with special relativity.

On the other hand, according to our hypothesis time has a minimum value (time quanta). So, time rate of something can not be infinite means mass in Kg unit can not be infinite in any region of space.

Now, let's try to think differently. Suppose, in an equilibrium dynamic quantum system a state of space moves in a loop. State of space exists for a time being in a point of that loop. So, mass related state element has an event value and event frequency in a point of that loop. Suppose, this frequency is f , event value is M and event duration is T .

Hence, According to our hypothesis mass in Kg unit in a point of the loop is-

$$Kg \equiv \frac{M}{T} = Mf \quad (14)$$

Total mass in that loop is the summation of mass in all points of the loop.

So, we can say that by Kg unit we actually measure time rate value of mass related state element of space of a region not intrinsic value of mass of that region.

If event duration (T) decrease means if speed of the state of space in the loop increases then mass in Kg unit increases. This is compatible with the special relativity theory. So, we can say that mass in the special theory of relativity of Einstein is also a time rate value not an intrinsic value. In that case loop must be treated as summation of many small linear path where speed of the state of space is linear and constant.

As mass in Kg unit increases with the speed of state of space in the loop, our so-called density of mass ($Kg/area$ or $Kg/volume$) on that loop region also increases.

From above discussion it can be said that in a region of space huge density of mass (here, high time rate value of mass (in Kg unit) on that region of space) is possible

if the speed of state of space is high enough in the loop. According to the hypotheses stated above a local event has its own minimum and non-zero quantized time duration (equivalent amount of independent chain of events). Hence, density of mass (in Kg unit) in a region of space cannot be infinite. This is a quantum scale explanation of huge density of mass at black hole.

Above discussion expel the local singularity as well as the singularity in time domain from the black hole.

VII. PHYSICAL ENTITY EXCEPT MASS

$100 - z$ percent contribution in the dynamic nature of a state of space is responsible for the sense of a physical entity. It means $100 - z$ percent of momentum is equivalent to a physical entity.

VIII. SPECIAL CASE

If the value of z is 100 percent then the whole momentum is equivalent to mass and there is not any other physical entity. This is so-called mass without any other physical entity.

On the other hand if the value of z is 0 percent then the whole momentum is equivalent to a physical entity and there is not any mass. This is so-called massless physical entity.

IX. SPACE IS ‘THE SAME THING’ OF EINSTEIN

According to the above discussion mass and energy are different manifestations of the structural dynamics of space. Hence, it can be said here that the term ‘the same thing’ in the comment of Einstein [7] is nothing but the ‘space’.

X. EXPLANATION OF WAVE-PARTICLE DUALITY

Let’s do a thought experiment classically.

Suppose, there is an $A4$ size paper in front of us. Area of one page is equal to L_1 and the other is L_2 . Though $L_1 = L_2$, direction of L_1 is opposite to L_2 . So, if we treat one area as positive then the other one must be treated as negative. This $A4$ size paper can spin/rotate (continuous swing) around an axis which is laid in its one surface along its long edge by dividing the paper in two equal parts. Now, if we stand keeping equal distance from short edges of the paper and look at it, then due to spin/rotation, value of area of the both pages will be appeared (result of interaction and here interaction is the reflection of incident light into paper to our eyes) to us in

a cosinusoidal shape (wave form). We see that area having fixed value (analogous to so-called particle) appeared to us with a value in wave manner due to spin/rotation process. Hence, it can be said here that the paper show wave-particle duality due to spin/rotation process. If this is a non-relativistic situation then in relativistic situation only the frequency of wave form will increase.

Now, let’s do same thought experiment quantum mechanically.

let’s imagine that size of the paper is very small (adequate for quantum mechanics). Moreover, we apply restriction on continuous spin/rotation. It means spin/rotation is allowed only in a discrete manner (discontinuous/discrete swing). Then the wave form will not in smooth cosinusoidal shape but due to spin/rotation process the paper will still show wave-particle duality.

Finally, in favor of our hypotheses we replace the very small size paper with a two dimensional state of space ($L_n \otimes \theta_n$) and approve discrete spin/rotation/swing due to the quantum nature of space [10]. Then a quantum entity governed by that two dimensional state of space will show the wave-particle duality.

From above discussion it can be said that wave-particle duality is due to the spin/rotation of a state of space. The frequency of wave is equal to spin/rotation frequency. The outer/open surface structure of the entity is responsible for the wave’s shape. Each term of Fourier series of that wave represents a $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ of the outer/open surface of that entity. Surface structure means angular relations (diversion of direction of one outer/open surface area from another) among the $L_n \otimes \theta_n$.

For above thought experiment peak value of the wave of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is $(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin \theta_s$, where, θ_s is the average angle between direction of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ and axis of spin/rotation.

Above discussion shows how a two dimensional state of space can create a two dimensional (when number of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is one) and three dimensional (when number of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is more than one) wave-particle duality.

Now, let’s try to explain one dimensional wave-particle duality. We start again from the above classical thought experiment.

If we shrink the paper along long edge upto quantum length (minimum length allowed by quantum mechanics) then it will become to a one dimensional element along the short edge. If our standing position and axis of rotation are same like above then due to spin/rotation length of the one dimensional element will be appeared (result of interaction and here interaction is the reflection of incident light into one dimensional paper to our eyes) to us in a cosinusoidal shape (wave form). We see that length having fixed value (analogous to so-called particle) appeared to us with a value in wave manner due to spin/rotation process. Hence, it can be said here that the one dimensional paper show wave-particle duality due to spin/rotation process. If this is a non-relativistic situation then in relativistic situation only the frequency of wave form will increase.

Now, let’s do same thought experiment quantum me-

chanically.

let's imagine that size of the one dimensional paper is very small (adequate for quantum mechanics). Moreover, we apply restriction on continuous spin/rotation. It means spin/rotation is allowed only in a discrete manner (discontinuous/discrete swing). Then the wave form will not in smooth sinusoidal shape but due to spin/rotation process the one dimensional paper will still show wave-particle duality.

Finally, in favor of our hypotheses we replace the very small size one dimensional paper with a one dimensional state of space ($L_n \otimes \theta_n$) and approve discrete spin/rotation/swing due to the quantum nature of space [10]. Then a quantum entity governed by that one dimensional state of space will show the wave-particle duality.

From above discussion it can be said that wave-particle duality is due to the spin/rotation of a state of space. The frequency of wave is equal to spin/rotation frequency.

The outer/open one dimensional structure of the entity is responsible for the wave's shape. Each term of Fourier series of that wave represents a $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ of the outer/open one dimensional structure of that entity. One dimensional structure means angular relations (diversion of direction of one outer/open one dimensional length from another) among the $L_n \otimes \theta_n$.

For above one dimensional thought experiment peak value of the wave of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is $(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin \theta_s$, where, θ_s is the average angle between direction of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ and axis of spin/rotation.

Above one dimensional discussion shows how a one dimensional state of space can create a one dimensional (when number of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is one) wave-particle duality.

Hence, we can say that hypotheses stated here are capable to explain wave-particle duality in the quantum world.

XI. DERIVATION OF SCHRÖDINGER WAVE FUNCTION FOR A TWO-DIMENSIONAL $L_n \otimes \theta_n$

Let's try to derive the Schrödinger wave function of single two dimensional $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ of the above thought experiment.

Here, $\theta_s = 90^\circ$. So, peak value is $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ and frequency of the wave is equal to the frequency of the spin.

Hence, in space dimation associated wave function of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$ is $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi)$ and

$$\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi) = Z(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \cos(\theta_\Psi) \quad (15)$$

Where, Z is a constant.

In order to bring $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi)$ in time domain we replace $\theta_\Psi = \omega t$ where, ω is angular frequency and take first order time derivative of $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi)$. Then,

$$\frac{\partial[\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(\theta_\Psi)]}{\partial t} = -Z\omega(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin(\omega t) \quad (16)$$

$$\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(t) = Z\omega(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin(-\omega t) \quad (17)$$

$Z\omega(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin(-\omega t)$ is a localized wave with 'time' variable at the location of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$, suppose at $x = 0$. It can be treated as a localized wave governed from a traveling wave in positive x direction then the traveling wave is-

$$\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t) = Z\omega(L_n \otimes \theta_n) \sin(kx - \omega t) \quad (18)$$

Where,

k is wave number.

Suppose, we have a quantum system consisting of R number of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Then $\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t)$ will be the associated wave function of our system because it travels through our system.

If we investigate then we will find that it has all qualities like Schrödinger wave function [$\Psi(x, t)$] of Schrodinger equation of a quantum system consists of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Hence, we can say that,

$$\Psi_{L_n \otimes \theta_n}(x, t) = \Psi(x, t) \quad (19)$$

Now, suppose a quantum size (minimum volume) ping pong ball is created using R number of $L_n \otimes \theta_n$. Then $\Psi(x, t)$ travels over the surface of that ball. If this traveling occurred around an axis then we can say that $\Psi(x, t)$ is spinning around that axis.

This spin of $\Psi(x, t)$ is responsible for spin angular momentum of that ball. By gaining spin angular momentum this ball increases its probability to sustain during an event.

XII. WE LIVE IN RELATIVE UNIVERSE

Suppose, an event chain $A_1 A_2 A_3 A_4 \dots$ consist a system A and another event chain $B_1 B_2 B_3 B_4 \dots$ consist a system B . Here, A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 etc. are events of respective event chain.

If A_1 and B_1 are synchronous, A_2 and B_2 are synchronous, A_3 and B_3 are synchronous and so on then according to the hypotheses stated in this paper, there is no relative time between these two systems. Hence, during the interaction between these two systems no system will sense any energy.

But if above mentioned event pairs are asynchronous then according to the hypotheses stated in this paper, there is a relative time between these two systems. Hence, during the interaction between these two systems both systems will sense energy. Energy will transfer from one system to another.

This finding is compatible to special theory of relativity.

Again suppose, above mentioned event pairs are asynchronous and these two systems consist a combined system AB . $L_1 \otimes \theta_1$ is a state of space in A and $L_2 \otimes \theta_2$ is a state of space in B . $\Psi_1(x, t)$ and $\Psi_2(x, t)$ are their respective associated wave function. $L_1 \otimes \theta_1$ and $L_2 \otimes \theta_2$ participate in an event.

As per previous discussion, due to that event, value of associated wave function will increase for one while decrease for other. Suppose, value of $\Psi_1(x, t)$ will increase by an amount of K while value of $\Psi_2(x, t)$ will decrease by an amount of K . In this situation measured energy is positive with respect to A while negative by same amount with respect to B . So, measured net energy in AB system is zero.

In the universe every event occurred in a combined system. Hence, in broader sense it can be said here that the universe always has net null energy.

Above discussion indicates that energy is not a fundamental physical element rather a relative mathematical element in the time domain discussion. It also implies that as there were no events on space before big bang, energy did not exist prior to the big bang and so the mass also.

It expels singularity issue from the big bang.

XIII. DURATION OF LOCAL EVENT IS HIGH IN A GRAVITATIONAL FIELD

Suppose, M and N are two regions of space. Gravitational field is high in M than N . That means density of deviated state of space suppose, G (responsible for gravitational field) is high at M than N . Now, we add a deviated state of space Q of same density in both regions of space. Density of Q is much lower than density of G . According to the hypothetical equation no. (13), probability of Q related events is low at M than that of N . Hence, it will need more time (an equivalent amount of an independent chain of events) in M than N for occurring same number of events related of Q . That means a local event of M takes more time (an equivalent amount of an independent chain of events) to be occurred than that of N .

In other words- according to the hypotheses stated above, there is no existence of time in a dynamic local physical system but only the events. According to the hypothetical equation no. (13), probability of Q related local events is less at M than N . So, if a third-party start counting the events both in M and N for same duration (for same amount of an independent chain of events), he will find a smaller number of events at M than N . Less number of events at M means an event of M takes more amount from an independent chain of events than that of N in time domain discussion.

When in a region of space $\sum_{i=1}^n d_i = d_{max}$ then, according to the equation no. (13) P_i is zero on that region of space. That means there is no local event and hence, this dynamic local physical system is out of time domain.

Then, this region of space is a saturated black hole.

It is a quantum explanation of slow event (so-called slow time) in a gravitational field.

XIV. WHITE HOLE

Suppose B is a region of space and at B , $\sum_{i=1}^n d_i = d_{max}$. Now, if further pressure is coming from an adjacent region of space to increase density of deviated state of space at B then, at first B will try not to take any more deviated state of space, if failed then it will try to find a channel in another adjacent region to release existing deviated state of space through it in order to receive new deviated state of space. If B doesn't find any releasing channel then due to continuous pressure from adjacent deviated state of space B may be destroyed or B may be restore itself to ground state of space by throwing all its existing deviated state of space to surrounding adjacent regions. During this ground state restoring process B can be called a white hole.

XV. SIGNIFICANCE OF $X_u = X_e/T$

If we compare equation no. (2) and (3) we can say that X_e is the event value of a physical entity X where h is the event value of energy (physical entity) of a photon, f is the frequency of both X_e and h , X_u is the time rate value (an element of time domain equation) of a physical entity X (may be concentrated deviated state of space or spreading deviated state of space) and E is the time rate value (an element of time domain equation) of energy of a photon (spreading deviated state of space).

We see that time domain equation no. (2) and (3) are similar.

XVI. DIFFRACTION AND INTERFERENCE OF LIGHT DUE TO NON-LINEAR PROPAGATION OF A PHOTON

According to our hypotheses we treat a photon as a deviated state of space, $L_x \otimes \theta_x$ having momentum p_x . We investigate the interaction between $L_x \otimes \theta_x$ and $L_0 \otimes \theta_0$. $L_0 \otimes \theta_0$ is ground state of space having momentum p_0 . Law of conservation of momentum is used to draw the propagation path of a photon after an event.

We know that probability is a fundamental phenomenon in quantum physics. Probabilistic situation is considered here to draw the path of propagation of a photon.

A. Non-linear propagation of a photon

Suppose, each schematic square in fig.1 is the necessary region (chunk) of space for the existence of a photon. Size

of the region (chunk) of space may be equal or more than the size of a space quantum. Each chunk of space in ground state means the whole space is homogeneous.

Fig.1: Two-dimensional schematic diagram of space for photon propagation.

Probable path of propagation of a photon from the region of space q_{17} is illustrated in fig.1.

Dynamic interaction occurred between photon and a region (chunk) of space. Law of conservation of momentum is obeyed in each event (interaction). Direction of momentum of a chunk of space and photon may be changed after each event. Hence, due to dynamic nature of $L_x \otimes \theta_x$ and $L_0 \otimes \theta_0$, a photon can go to any adjacent region of space from a region of space.

We start our investigation from going of photon from the region of space q_{17} to the region of space q_5 .

Let, probability of photon transfer from the region of space q_{17} to the region of space q_5 is $P_{(x)(5)} = a$ and here, x for photon, P for probability, 5 for probability of photon incoming to the region of space q_5 .

As photon comes from q_{17} to q_5 , photon can go from q_5 to q_{18} , q_{17} , q_{16} , q_4 , q_3 , q_0 , q_7 , q_6 . But for simplicity we consider only q_5 to q_3 , q_0 , q_7 . That means only forward direction. Observation also says that probability in these directions are more than the others. This consideration also for outgoing of a photon from q_3 , q_0 , q_7 .

Now, as this space is homogeneous-

For outgoing of a photon from q_5 , $P_{(x)(7)} = P_{(x)(0)} = P_{(x)(3)} = a/3$

For outgoing of a photon from q_7 , $P_{(x)(22)} = P_{(x)(8)} = P_{(x)(1)} = a/9$

For outgoing of a photon from q_0 , $P_{(x)(8)} = P_{(x)(1)} = P_{(x)(2)} = a/9$

For outgoing of a photon from q_3 , $P_{(x)(1)} = P_{(x)(2)} = P_{(x)(12)} = a/9$

So, total probability for q_8 = total probability for $q_2 = a/9 + a/9 = 2a/9$

Total probability for $q_1 = a/9 + a/9 + a/9 = a/3$

Total probability for $q_{22} =$ total probability for $q_{12} = a/9$

It should be noted here that due to quantum nature of space probability of photon incoming in a region of space cannot be arbitrary.

Now, let's give completeness to our present situation, like as below-

If we measure photon energy at q_3 , q_0 , q_7 , q_{22} , q_8 , q_1, q_2 , q_{12} for a time duration equal to time duration for 9 photons passing through q_5 we will find the photon energy according to their probability value.

For example, if E is energy for a single photon then energy at $q_1 = (9E)a/3 = 3aE$, energy at $q_2 =$ energy at $q_8 = (9E)2a/9 = 2aE$ and energy at $q_{22} =$ energy at $q_{12} = (9E)a/9 = aE$.

As we assume that 9 photons pass through q_5 , so value of a for all 9 photons is 1.

Hence, energy at $q_1 = 3aE = 3E$, energy at $q_2 =$ energy at $q_8 = 2aE = 2E$ and energy at $q_{22} =$ energy at $q_{12} = aE = E$.

Total energy at q_1 , q_2 , q_8 , q_{22} and q_{12} is $3E + 2E + 2E + E + E = 9E$, which is equal to the total energy passing through q_5 .

We see that conservation of energy is obeyed here.

For example, among the other $q_{17} - q_5 - q_7 - q_1$, $q_{17} - q_5 - q_3 - q_1$ are non-linear paths for propagation of a photon.

This situation is only for a single directed photon. If photon is emitted from q_5 in every possible direction then all possible regions of space at particular distance from q_5 have equal probability value, means all possible regions of space at particular distance from q_5 have equal photon energy.

B. Diffraction of photon (light)

Fig.2: Two-dimensional schematic diagram of space for photon propagation and diffraction.

Now, let's try to explain diffraction of light.

Suppose, q_0 is unavailable for photon. Then situation will be like fig.2.

So,

For outgoing of photon from q_5 , $P_{(x)(7)} = P_{(x)(3)} = a/2$

For outgoing of photon from q_7 , $P_{(x)(22)} = P_{(x)(8)} = P_{(x)(1)} = a/6$

For outgoing of photon from q_3 , $P_{(x)(1)} = P_{(x)(2)} = P_{(x)(12)} = a/6$

So, total probability for $q_{22} =$ total probability for $q_8 =$ total probability for $q_2 =$ total probability for $q_{12} = a/6$
 Total probability for $q_1 = a/6 + a/6 = a/3$

Now, let's give completeness to our present situation, like as below-

If we measure photon energy at $q_3, q_7, q_{22}, q_8, q_1, q_2, q_{12}$ for a time duration equal to time duration for 6 photons passing through q_5 we will find the photon energy according to their probability value.

For example, if E is energy for a single photon then energy at $q_1 = (6E)a/3 = 2aE$, energy at $q_{22} =$ energy at $q_8 =$ energy at $q_2 =$ energy at $q_{12} = (6E)a/6 = aE$

As we assume that 6 photons pass through q_5 , so value of a for all 6 photons is 1.

Hence, energy at $q_1 = 2aE = 2E$, energy at $q_{22} =$ energy at $q_8 =$ energy at $q_2 =$ energy at $q_{12} = aE = E$

Total energy at q_1, q_{22}, q_8, q_2 and q_{12} is $2E + E + E + E + E = 6E$, which is equal to the total energy passing through q_5 .

We see that conservation of energy is obeyed here.

In spite of unavailability of q_0 for a photon, due to non-linear path $q_{17} - q_5 - q_7 - q_1, q_{17} - q_5 - q_3 - q_1$ of a photon, energy is available at q_1 .

This is diffraction of light.

Here, we see that diffraction of light can be explained by dynamic interaction between a photon ($L_x \otimes \theta_x$) and a chunk of space ($L_0 \otimes \theta_0$).

C. Interference of photon (light)

In a region (chunk) of space, suppose S , net incoming probability of photon from different region (chunk) of space (different sources of photon) is

$$P_{(net)} = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i P_{(i)} \quad (20)$$

Here,

$$0 \leq \sum_{i=1}^n b_i P_{(i)} \leq 1 \quad (21)$$

and

$$0 \leq b_i \leq 1 \quad (22)$$

$P_{(net)}$ is net incoming probability of photon from different sources into S region of space.

$P_{(i)}$ is incoming probability of a photon from i^{th} source when there is no other photon source for S .

n is the total number of photon source.

b_i is coefficient for i^{th} source with presence of n number of photon sources. Value of b_i depends on the frequencies of the sources and on dynamics of the intermediate chunk of space (here, chunks of space from the source's region of space to the destination region of space). Suppose,

this dynamics is represented by $L_0 \otimes \theta_0$ (according to our hypotheses). Due to quantum nature of space b_i cannot be arbitrary.

Product of two non-arbitrary (b_i, P_i) elements makes P_{net} more discrete for the adjacent regions of S . Hence, we find discrete spectrum in S and its adjacent regions.

If a photon has energy E then net energy in S region of space.

$$E_{net} = nEP_{(net)} \quad (23)$$

If, $P_{net} = 0$, then $E_{net} = 0$. This is destructive interference.

If, $P_{net} = 1$, then $E_{net} = nE$. This is constructive interference.

XVII. CONCLUSION

Getting inspiration from the thoughts of A. Einstein [1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9], Newton, C. Rovelli and L. Smolin [10], Erwin Schrödinger structural dynamics of space has been treated here as the fundamental cause of any entity of the universe. It is also declared here that time domain descriptions of the entities are essential only for comparative discussion among their space domain descriptions and among their events in space domain. It means time is treated here only as a mathematical term not a physical element.

Findings of Kg unit as a 'time rate quantity' is compatible with special theory of relativity [1,2,3,4], because it is the time rate value not the intrinsic value of an entity which can vary with speed. Thus, it consistent with huge but finite mass density of black hole

Mass and energy are expressed as different manifestations of associated wave function of a state of space. So, space is the candidate for being 'the same thing' of the comment of A. Einstein [7].

Hypotheses and findings of this paper is a step forward to establish the idea of quantum nature of space [10]. It should be noted here that space is already treated as fundamental element in the special theory of relativity [3,4], the general theory of relativity [8,9] and the loop quantum gravity theory.

Here is a new understanding of energy and a road map for unification of all fundamental forces (time domain descriptions).

Structural dynamics of space is the cause of wave-particle duality in quantum world. Here is a back ground philosophy for Schrödinger wave function.

Here is an indication that diffraction and interference of light can be explained by the quantum theory of light as well as by the wave theory of light.

Not only the diffraction and interference of light but also diffraction and interference of all quantum scaled entity can be explained by this technique.

In a nut shell, space is the only candidate to be the fundamental element of the universe.

Data availability

This content is available in the <https://zenodo.org> repository. All versions including the latest one is in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275710>

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